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Research Article

Formulation and Characterization of Herbal Tablets for the Management of Anti-microbial Activity

Aishwarya Thakur*, Omkar Salunkhe, Bhavita Shirodkar, Anushka Shetkar, Sanchita Pednekar, Shruti Gawade

Yashwantrao Bhonsale College of Pharmacy, Sawantwadi, Sindhudurg, Maharashtra, India 416510

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ABSTRACT

Tablets were formulated using Euphorbia hirta plant extract through the wet granulation technique. In this study, the aerial parts of Euphorbia hirta were used for the preparation of herbal tablets. The extract was obtained by maceration followed by Soxhlet extraction methods, then dried and blended. After extraction, the dried herbal material was mixed with pharmaceutical excipients such as diluents, binders, super disintegrants, and lubricants to prepare granules. The prepared granules were evaluated for their physical properties, including the Angle of repose, Bulk and tapped density, Carr's Index, Hausner's Ratio, Void volume. These granules were then compressed into tablets of specific size and shape using a tablet punching machine. Once the tablets were prepared, they were tested for various evaluation parameters such as Physical appearance, Weight variation, Friability, Disintegration time, Hardness, Thickness, Flavour and taste for patient acceptability. The formulated Euphorbia hirta tablets showed acceptable physical properties such as uniform weight, hardness, and rapid disintegration time. Additionally, the extract exhibited significant antimicrobial activity, indicating its potential effectiveness against common bacterial strains.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines have gained significant attention in the modern pharmaceutical industry due to their wide therapeutic benefits, biocompatibility, and lower risk of side effects compared to synthetic drugs. With the growing concern over antibiotic resistance and adverse reactions to conventional

antimicrobial agents, there is a renewed interest in exploring plant-based alternatives. Among the various dosage forms, tablets are one of the most widely used and accepted forms of drug delivery due to their convenience, stability, ease of administration, and patient compliance.[1] Euphorbia hirta, a medicinal herb belonging to the

*Corresponding Author: Aishwarya Thakur

Address: Yashwantrao Bhonsale College of Pharmacy, Sawantwadi, Sindhudurg, Maharashtra, India 416510

Email ✉: thakuraishwarya69@gmail.com

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Euphorbiaceous family, is traditionally used in various systems of medicine, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. It is known for its diverse pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antiasthmatic, antidiarrheal, and wound healing properties. The plant contains active phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, and essential oils, which are responsible for its biological activities. Its antimicrobial effect has been particularly noted against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, making it a promising candidate for developing alternative therapies for microbial infections. [7] In the present study, an attempt has been made to formulate and characterize herbal tablets containing *Euphorbia hirta* extract using the wet granulation technique. The formulation involves the use of various pharmaceutical excipients like diluents, binders, disintegrants, and lubricants to ensure uniformity and acceptable mechanical properties of the tablets. Postformulation, the tablets were evaluated for standard quality control parameters such as hardness, friability, disintegration time, weight variation, thickness, and organoleptic properties. [7] Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of the *Euphorbia hirta* extract was assessed using methods like agar well diffusion or disc diffusion, targeting common microbial strains to validate its therapeutic efficacy. The primary objective of this work is to develop a standardized, effective, and patient-friendly herbal dosage form that can be used in the management and prevention of microbial infections, especially in the context of rising antimicrobial resistance. [8] This study aims to bridge the gap between traditional herbal knowledge and modern pharmaceutical sciences by developing a reliable, natural antimicrobial agent in tablet form, which can contribute to the growing field of phytopharmaceuticals and integrative medicine. [8]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Raw Material:- *Euphorbia hirta* Extract, Fractional Flavonoidal content of *Euphorbia hirta* Extract.

Chemicals/ Reagents:- Methanol, Petroleum Ether, Aluminum Chloride, Sodium Hydroxide, Ethyl Acetate, Dil. Ammonia HCL, Peptone Beef Extract, Sodium Chloride, Dichloromethane, Starch, Aerosil, Magnesium Stearate, Talc, Mannitol, Sodium Bicarbonate, NH₄OH, Distilled Water, Citric acid, Chloroform, PVP, etc.

Instruments/ Accessories:- Electronic Balance, Soxhlet Apparatus, Water Bath, Sonicator, Hot Air Oven, Colorimeter, Laminar Air Flow, Incubator, Tablet Hardness Tester, Disintegration Test Apparatus, Friability Tester, Dissolution Tester, Tablet Thickness and Diameter Gauge, Analytical Balance (for Weight Variation Test), Powder Flow Tester, Vernier Caliper (for dimension measurement), Bulk Density Apparatus, Tapped Density Tester, Angle of Repose Apparatus, Tablet Compression Machine, etc.

Methods:

PREPARATION OF EUPHORBIA PLANT EXTRACTS:

- i. Determination of Alcohol Soluble Extractive Value: Weighed accurately 4 grams of sample was macerated with 100 ml of alcohol in a conical flask for 24 hours, with frequent shaking at an interval of 6 hours. It was then allowed to stand for 18 hours and filtered rapidly to prevent any loss during evaporation. 25 ml of filtrate was evaporated until it dries in a porcelain dish and dried at 105°C to a constant weight. The percentage of alcohol soluble extract was calculated with reference to air-dried material.

[1]

- ii. **Extraction Method:** Coarsely powdered plant material was subjected to cold maceration with methanol with occasional shaking. Extract was filtered through Whatman's filter paper and the filtrate was collected in clean glass container. Mare was dried and subjected to Soxhlet extraction using methanol (till the colored extract become colorless) at 40°C. Extract was mixed with filtrate of cold maceration. A total extract was concentrated by using water bath. Obtained concentrated extract was dried and stored in air tight container. [2]
- iii. **Fractionation of Flavonoid:** Extract the sample (crude plant material) in suitable solvent. Evaporate it at 40°C to obtain residue. The obtaining residue is dissolved in 2 diff. parts of citric acid & dichloromethane. X gm. of sample dissolved in X ml of 5% citric acid. Add 25ml of dichloromethane keep it for 10 min for separation. Separate the dichloromethane & aqueous layer in separating funnel. Evaporate both liquid to dryness. Dichloromethane residue is dissolve in petroleum Ether & 90% methanol in the ratio of (1:1). In next step we get two layers of petroleum ether and methanol. In petroleum ether consist of lipids & waxes whereas methanol layer contains phenolic, terpenes & sterols. The obtained fractions are used for further phytochemical testing. [3]
- iv. **Phytochemical Screening:**
 1. **Alkaline reagent test-** Add 5 drops of dilute sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to 2 ml of plant extract, then add diluted hydrochloric acid (HCl). If the yellow solution turns colorless, flavonoids are present.
 2. **Ammonium test-** Heat 10 ml of ethyl acetate with the extraction in boiling water for 3 minutes, then filter. Mix the filtrate with 1 ml of dilute ammonia solution, then shake. If the ammonia layer is not yellow, flavonoids are present.
 3. **Shinoda test-** Add 2-3 ml of filtrate extraction with magnesium metal, then add HCL concentrate. If the color is magenta, flavonoids are present. [4]
 - v. **Determination of Total flavonoid content:** The total flavonoid content (TFC) in plants can be determined using a colorimetric assay with aluminum chloride. Add 100 microliters of extract to 4 milliliters of distilled water. Add 0.3 milliliters of 5% sodium nitrite. After 5 minutes, add 0.3 milliliters of 10% aluminum chloride. After 6 minutes, add 2 milliliters of 1 M sodium hydroxide. Immediately, add 3.3 milliliters of distilled water and mix thoroughly. Then the sample solutions were prepared in concentration range of (0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1) mg/ml. Determine the absorbance at 510 nanometers versus a blank. Similarly, the standard solution of quercetin was prepared in range of (0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1) mg/ml. Calculate the TFC using a calibration curve. [4]

FORMULATION OF HERBAL TABLETS:

Method of Preparation of Herbal Tablet: Herbal tablets were prepared using the wet granulation method. Wet dough mass was passed through sieve no. 16 for uniform granules. Granules were air dried for 3–4 hours. Further drying was done in a hot air oven at 45°C–50°C for 20–30 minutes. Dried granules were sieved again for uniformity. Magnesium stearate and talc were added as lubricants. Granules were compressed using a tablet compression machine. Tablet hardness was maintained at a maximum of 4 kg/cm². [9]

Table No. 1: The formula for the Herbal Anti-microbial tablet (per 500mg) in mg

Sr. No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Flavonoid	2.25	1.25	3.25	2	4
2.	Starch	112.5	111.5	113.5	112	114
3.	PVP	37.5	37.5	37.5	37.5	37.5

4.	Aerosil	20	20	20	20	20
5.	Magnesium Stearate	15	15	15	15	15
6.	Talc	15	15	15	15	15
7.	Mannitol	285.75	287.75	283.75	286.50	282.50
8.	Sodium Bicarbonate	12	12	12	12	12

EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF TABLETS: [9]

1) Pre-compression Evaluation Parameters:

- Angle of Repose: Powder is poured from a funnel onto a horizontal surface; it will form a cone due to gravitational forces. The angle between the sides of the cone and the horizontal is referred to as the angle of repose. The angle of repose is a relatively simple technique for estimation of the flow property of powder. Powders with low angle of repose are free flowing and those with a high angle of repose are poorly flowing powders. 10gm of granules were passed through funnel and the pile was formed.

$$\text{Angle of Repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$$

- Bulk Density: This is obtained to know the exact volume of the granules that is being placed in the cylinder. Initials are used in the formula. Bulk density is also known as the fluff and poured density.

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \text{Mass (M)} / \text{Volume (V)}$$

- Tapped Density: It is obtained with the help of tap density apparatus, in which the powder is filled in the cylinders and the tapping is done. After few times of intervals the volume of the cylinder is noted down and the tapped density of the granules.

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Weight (W)} / \text{Volume after 50 taps (V}_{50})$$

- Carr's Index: After obtaining the tapped and fluff density, the Carr's Index is being calculated by using 100ml measuring cylinder.

$$\% \text{ Compressibility} = [(\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}) / \text{Tapped Density}] \times 100$$

- Hausner's Ratio: Calculate the ratio of tapped density to poured density.

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio} = \text{Tapped Density} / \text{Bulk Density}$$

- Void Volume: This volume of the granules is obtained by using the values of bulk volume and tapped density. This will indicate the air volumes that is being created in the granules during tapping.

$$\text{Void Volume} = \text{Bulk Volume} - \text{Tapped Volume}$$

2) Post-compression Evaluation Parameters:

- Weight Variation: 10 tablets were selected randomly and weight individually. The average of tablets is calculated using formula and the Standard deviation is calculated by using formula.

$$\text{S.D.} = \sqrt{(\sum D^2 / N)}$$

- Hardness Test: This test is done using the Monsanto and Pfizer apparatus. In this the tablet is kept in its place in the apparatus and the pressure is applied to it. The pressure is noted down which have been recorded by the pressure gauge and average hardness is calculated.
- Friability Test: This test is carried out by using Friability apparatus. The weighted tablets are placed in the apparatus and it is rotated at 25 rpm for 5 minutes. After sometimes tablets are removed out from apparatus and again they are weight.

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = [(W_i - W_f) / W_i] \times 100$$

- Disintegration Test: Take 3 tablets are taken for the evaluation of the disintegration time. The tablets are placed in the disintegration

apparatus and the time is observed till the tablet gets totally disintegrated. The temperature of the apparatus is maintained at 37° C.

- **Tablet Thickness Test:** Tablets are placed one by one in a Vernier caliper or digital thickness gauge. The thickness is measured in millimetres (mm).
- **Dissolution Study:** At each time point, an equal volume of the sample was withdrawn. It was replaced with the same volume of pre-warmed fresh dissolution medium to maintain sink condition. The amount of drug released was determined spectrophotometrically at the selected wavelength of 203 nm. [10]

MICROBIAL ASSAY:

1) **Assay of anti-bacterial activity:** Assay of anti-microbial activity of herbal tablet and standard solution of azithromycin tablet was done by Disc Diffusion method. In this method 100ml of sterilized Nutrient Agar was equally poured into 2 sterile petri plates, after solidification, 120µl of bacterial culture poured on the plates and the culture was spread on plates using spreader. Then, the Whatman's filter paper discs (6mm in diameter) were kept over the 2 agar plates using sterile forceps at various concentrations. First prepare plate containing the standard azithromycin solution, second plate containing the herbal tablet solution. The anti-bacterial assay plates were kept incubator, where all the plates were incubated at

37°c for 24hours. The diameter of inhibition zone was noted down. [3]

Table No.2: Formula for Nutrient Agar

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Qty. Taken
1.	Agar	2 gm.
2.	Peptone	1 gm.
3.	Beef Extract	1 gm.
4.	Sodium Chloride	0.5 gm.
5.	Distilled Water	100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of Alcohol Soluble Extractive Value:

The Extractive Value (Methanol as a solvent) of the Euphorbia Hirta was found to be 7.2 % w/w. The Standard Extractive Value of the Euphorbia Hirta is 9.71 % w/w.

Extraction and Fractionation of Plant Material:

The methanol extract of Euphorbia Hirta Plant was prepared and used for further studies. Extract was dark green in colour. Obtained extract was subjected to fractionation for separation of Flavonoids. Methanol fraction was used for study the anti-microbial activity.

Phytochemical Screening:

Obtained result of phytochemical screening of Isolated Flavonoids from Euphorbia are as follow;

Table No. 3: Phytochemical Tests

Sr. No.	Phytochemical Test for Flavonoids	Observations	Conclusion
1.	Shinoda test	Magenta color is observed	Flavonoids are present
2.	Alkaline reagent test	Yellow solution turns colorless	Flavonoids are present
3.	Ammonium test	Ammonia layer is not yellow	Flavonoids are present

Figure 1: Phytochemicals Tests

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content:

The total flavonoid content of euphorbia hirta was found to be 11.57 mg QE/g of sample by

colorimetric assay method. The TFC of Quercetin can range from 87.53 ± 0.30 mg QE/g. Thus, the total flavonoid content (TFC) of Euphorbia hirta is lies between the TFC of Quercetin.

Table No.4: Observation Table

Sr. No.	Concentration (mg/ml)	Absorbance
1.	0	0
2.	0.2	0.13
3.	0.4	0.14
4.	0.6	0.20
5.	0.8	0.25
6.	1	0.29
7.	UNKNOWN	0.25

Figure 2: Calibration curve for quercetin

Pre-compression Evaluation Parameters:

The Evaluation Parameters Angle of Repose, Tapped Density, Bulk Density, Carr's Index,

Hausner's Ratio and Void Volume Were Carried Out for the Granules of F1, F2, F3, F4, & F5 are showed as follow;

Table No. 5: Showing Different Evaluation Parameters of Granules of F1, F2, F3, F4 & F5.

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Angle of Repose	26.570	21.800	21.800	21.800	21.800
2.	Tapped Density	0.45 gm/ml	0.64 gm/ml	0.60 gm/ml	0.65 gm/ml	0.66 gm/ml
3.	Bulk Density	0.34 gm/ml	0.52 gm/ml	0.54 gm/ml	0.55 gm/ml	0.52 gm/ml
4.	Carr's Index	24	19	10	15.38	21.21
5.	Hausner's Ratio	1.32	1.23	1.11	1.18	1.27
6.	Void Volume	4 ml	1.8 ml	1 ml	1.5 ml	2 ml

Post-compression Evaluation Parameters:

The Evaluation Parameters like Physical Appearance, Weight Variation, Friability, Hardness, Thickness and Disintegration Test Were

Carried for the F1, F2, F3, F4 & F5 are shown as follow;

Table No. 6: Showing Different Evaluation Parameters of Tablets of F1, F2, F3, F4 & F5.

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameters		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Physical Appearance	Color	Greenish white				
		Odor	Musty	Musty	Musty	Musty	Musty
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round
		Diameter(cm)	1	1	1	1	1
2.	Weight Variation (%)		0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
3.	Friability (%)		0.79	0.40	0.50	0.29	0.39
4.	Hardness (kg/cm ²)		5	7.5	1	8.5	8
5.	Thickness (mm)		5.03	5.05	4.97	5.06	5.16
6.	Disintegration Time (min)		9	5:03	6:22	9:11	8:02

Dissolution Study:

The percentage drug release record mentioned in the table as per particular seconds. The graph shows that the formulation number F1 (80%) has

the highest drug release and formulation number F5 (32.60%) is the very less drug release. So, we choose the formulation number F1 for study the anti-microbial activity.

Table No. 7: The % drug release record mentioned in the table as per particular seconds.

Sr. No.	Time (Seconds)	% Drug Release Record				
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	90	10	-6.35	6.89	0.47	0.25
2.	180	30	0.77	11.28	9	5.61
3.	270	40	13.28	20.28	16.43	10.47
4.	360	50	21.89	35.42	20.06	16.85
5.	450	60	28.01	39.69	25.89	20.68
6.	560	70	35.95	51.84	34.21	22.58
7.	630	80	46.32	62.15	38.75	26.16
8.	720	80	52.36	67.87	44.24	32.60

Figure 3: The Percentage drug release record mentioned in the graph

Microbial Assay:

Antimicrobial activity refers to any action that destroys bacteria or inhibits their growth and reproduction. This can be achieved through heat, chemicals such as chlorine, and antibiotic drugs, all of which possess antimicrobial properties. Antimicrobials are commonly used to treat bacterial

infections and are generally considered to have low toxicity in humans and other animals. However, they may have negative health effects in some cases. The Herbal Tablets (Batch No. F1) prepared from Isolated Flavonoid of *Euphorbia hirta* shows the anti-microbial activity against the *Escherichia coli*.

Figure 4: Assay of Standard Solution

Figure 5: Assay of Herbal Tablets

CONCLUSION:

The formulation and characterization of herbal tablets for the management of antimicrobial activity have yielded promising results, indicating the potential of herbal medicine as a natural and effective alternative to conventional antibiotics. In this study, selected medicinal plants known for their antimicrobial properties were successfully incorporated into a tablet dosage form using appropriate excipients and standard pharmaceutical techniques. The tablets were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as hardness, friability, disintegration time, and weight variation, all of which were found to be within acceptable limits. These results confirm the mechanical strength, stability, and uniformity of the formulated tablets, ensuring their suitability for oral administration. Phytochemical screening

confirmed the presence of bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic, which are known contributors to antimicrobial activity. The antimicrobial testing, conducted against a range of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, demonstrated that the herbal tablets possess significant inhibitory effects, supporting the therapeutic potential of the formulation. Overall, this research highlights the importance of herbal formulations in the fight against microbial resistance, a growing global concern due to the overuse and misuse of synthetic antibiotics. The study sets the groundwork for further investigations, including in vivo studies and clinical trials, to fully establish the efficacy, safety, and therapeutic potential of these herbal tablets. If validated through further research, such formulations can play a vital role in the development of cost-effective, accessible, and

eco-friendly antimicrobial therapies, especially in regions where access to modern medicine is limited.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST: NIL

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